

Analysis of modulated photoluminescence for lifetime determination in silicon

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Overview

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- Concept of Modulated Photoluminescence (MPL)
- Linear models and experimental results
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 - bimolecular approach
- MPL and open circuit voltage
- Summary

Introduction

- Open-circuit voltage V_{OC} of a-Si:H/c-Si heterodiode solar cells depends to large degree on interface defect density
- Efficient passivation of surfaces is required
- Effective lifetime = indicator for interface quality
- **Modulated photoluminescence (MPL)**: efficient and simple method for lifetime measurement allows investigation of influence of interface defects on minority carrier lifetime and estimation for V_{OC} in c-Si

Lifetime measurement

Established methods:

- **Microwave photoconductance decay (μ -PCD)**
- **Quasi-steady-state photoconductance (QSSPC)**

Problem: high concentration of free carriers (metallic defects, metallic rear contacts, high doped layers)

→ conductive methods fail because of shielding effects

→ alternative method: MPL

Concept: MPL

Considering high quality wafers with high bulk lifetime, the effective lifetime is determined by the contribution of surface/passivation layers (recombination velocities):

$$\frac{1}{\tau_{eff}} = \frac{1}{\tau_{bulk}} + \frac{S_1}{W} + \frac{S_2}{W}$$

D : diffusion coefficient

S_1, S_2 : recombination velocities

W : wafer thickness

n_0, p_0 : carrier concentration

Concept: MPL

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n_0, p_0 : carrier concentration; Δn : excess carrier density

Concept: MPL

Optical excitation with modulation frequency ω

Response with modulation frequency ω
and delay time = **effective lifetime** τ_{eff}

Amplitude and phase of response depend
on effective lifetime τ_{eff}

With Lock-In technique get amplitude and
phase spectra

Lock-in: phase-sensitive detection

In-phase/ out-of-phase components:

$$S_{IP}(\omega) = \frac{2}{T} \int_0^T S(t) \cos(\omega t) dt$$

$$U(\omega) = \sqrt{S_{IP}(\omega)^2 + S_{OP}(\omega)^2}$$

$$S_{OP}(\omega) = \frac{2}{T} \int_0^T S(t) \sin(\omega t) dt$$

$$\phi(\omega) = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{S_{OP}(\omega)}{S_{IP}(\omega)} \right)$$

Experimental setup

Samples

p,n-type c-Si wafer with different passivation:

- different passivation layers: n-type, intrinsic, SiC, a-Si:H, SiN

- different doping ($N_A=10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $N_A=10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$)

- wafer with TCO and rear contact (solar cell)

Simple model [1]

Rate equation with sinusoidal modulation:

$$\frac{d\Delta n(t)}{dt} = G(t) - R(t) = G_0 + G_1 \sin(\omega t) - \frac{\Delta n(t)}{\tau}$$

$$\Delta n(t) = G_0\tau + G_1\tau \frac{\sin(\omega t + \arctan(\omega\tau))}{\sqrt{1 + (\omega\tau)^2}}$$

spectral amplitude: $\Delta n_1(\omega) = \frac{\Delta G_1\tau}{\sqrt{1 + (\omega\tau)^2}}$

spectral phase: $\varphi(\omega) = -\arctan(\omega\tau) \Leftrightarrow \tan(\varphi) = -\omega\tau$

Results: SiC-passivation (1 Ωcm)

two procedures for lifetime extraction from experimental measurement

fit amplitude

$$\tau_n = 397 \mu\text{s}$$

$$|\Delta n_1| = \frac{\tau_n G_1}{\sqrt{1 + (\omega \tau_n)^2}}$$

fit tangent

$$\tau_n = 405 \mu\text{s}$$

$$\tan(\varphi) = -\omega \tau_n$$

Results: SiN passivation (1 Ωcm)

lifetime measurement by phase more reliable in contrast to amplitude

τ_ϕ

$\tau_{\text{amplitude}}$

$$\Delta n = G\tau_{\text{eff}}$$

Results: SiN passivation (1 Ωcm)

good agreement between measurement at rear and front side

τ_ϕ

$\tau_{\text{amplitude}}$

$$\Delta n = G\tau_{\text{eff}}$$

Results: (n)a-Si-H/(i)a-Si:H pass. (1 Ωcm)

applied to solar cell (only in reflection mode)

τ_ϕ

$\tau_{\text{amplitude}}$

$$\Delta n = G\tau_{\text{eff}}$$

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high frequency range: deviations from linear variation of the tangens

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Better approach: solving diffusion equation [2]

$$\frac{\partial \Delta n(x, t)}{\partial t} = D \nabla^2 \Delta n(x, t) - \frac{\Delta n(x, t)}{\tau_{bulk}} + G(x, t)$$

Δn : excess carrier density

D : diffusion coefficient

G : generation rate

Better approach: solving diffusion equation [2]

$$\frac{\partial \Delta n(x, t)}{\partial t} = D \nabla^2 \Delta n(x, t) - \frac{\Delta n(x, t)}{\tau_{bulk}} + G(x, t)$$

$$G(x, t) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} G_m e^{im\omega t} e^{-\alpha x} \quad \begin{aligned} D \frac{\partial \Delta n(x, t)}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=0} &= S_1 \Delta n(0, t) \\ - D \frac{\partial \Delta n(x, t)}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=W} &= S_2 \Delta n(W, t) \end{aligned}$$

Δn : excess carrier density

D : diffusion coefficient

G : generation rate

α : absorption coefficient

S_1, S_2 surface recombination velocity

Complex solution: local excess carrier concentration

$$\Delta n(x, t) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \Delta n_m^*(x, \omega) e^{im\omega t}$$

Solution: complex excess carrier concentration

$$\Delta n(x, t) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \Delta n_m^*(x, \omega) e^{im\omega t}$$

$$\sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \int_0^W \Delta n_m^*(x, \omega) e^{im\omega t} dx = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \Delta N_m^*(\omega) e^{im\omega t}$$

W : wafer thickness

Lock-In detection: only fundamental component (ω)

$$\Delta n_1^*(x, \omega) = \frac{G_1 \left(C_1 e^{(x-W)/L_1} + C_2 e^{-(x-W)/L_1} - e^{\alpha x} \right)}{D \left(\alpha^2 - \frac{1}{L_1^2} \right)}$$

$$C_1 = \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\alpha D + S_1) \left(\frac{D}{L_1} - S_2 \right) - (\alpha D - S_2) \left(\frac{D}{L_1} + S_1 \right) e^{-W(\alpha - \frac{1}{L_1})}}{\left(\frac{D^2}{L_1^2} + S_1 S_2 \right) \sinh\left(\frac{W}{L_1}\right) + \frac{D}{L_1} (S_1 + S_2) \cosh\left(\frac{W}{L_1}\right)}$$

$$\tau_1(\omega) = \frac{\tau_{bulk}}{1 + i\omega\tau_{bulk}}$$

$$C_2 = \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\alpha D + S_1) \left(\frac{D}{L_1} + S_2 \right) - (\alpha D - S_2) \left(\frac{D}{L_1} - S_1 \right) e^{-W(\alpha + \frac{1}{L_1})}}{\left(\frac{D^2}{L_1^2} + S_1 S_2 \right) \sinh\left(\frac{W}{L_1}\right) + \frac{D}{L_1} (S_1 + S_2) \cosh\left(\frac{W}{L_1}\right)}$$

$$L_1(\omega) = \sqrt{D\tau_1(\omega)}$$

L_1 : diffusion length

Extended model

- more precise model including independent values for front and back surface recombination velocities, wavelength dependent absorption, sample thickness and dopant type

$$U_{ampl} \sim \left\| \int_0^W \Delta n_1^*(x, \omega) dx \right\| = \left\| \Delta N_1^*(\omega) \right\|$$

$$\phi(\omega) = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\Im(\Delta N_1^*(\omega))}{\Re(\Delta N_1^*(\omega))} \right)$$

- model allows depth profile of amplitude and phase spectra

Space depending amplitude and phase spectra

$$D = 12 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}; \quad \tau_{\text{bulk}} = 20 \text{ ms}; \quad W = 0.025 \text{ cm}; \quad \alpha = 1010 \text{ cm}^{-1};$$

symmetrical sample: $S_1 = S_2 = 20, 100, 500, 10^3, 10^4, 10^6 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$

Integrated amplitude and phase spectra

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Integrated amplitude and phase spectra

overestimation of real lifetime for high surface recombination rates

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$$D = 12 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}; \tau_{\text{bulk}} = 20 \text{ ms}; W = 0.025 \text{ cm}; \alpha = 1010 \text{ cm}^{-1};$$

asymmetrical sample: $S_L = 50, 100, 500, 10^3, 10^4, 10^6 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$; $S_r = 20 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$

Integrated amplitude and phase spectra

$$D = 12 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}; \tau_{\text{bulk}} = 20 \text{ ms}; W = 0.025 \text{ cm}; \alpha = 1010 \text{ cm}^{-1};$$

asymmetrical sample: $S_1 = 50, 100, 500, 10^3, 10^4, 10^6 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$; $S_2 = 20 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$

Integrated amplitude and phase spectra

overestimation of real lifetime for high surface recombination rates

Simple model vs. exact solution of diffusion equation

- good agreement of spectra for low frequencies
- good agreement of lifetimes for $S_i < 200 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$
- simple model overestimates the effective lifetime for high surface recombination velocities
- exact solution of the diffusion equation does not explain nonlinear deviations in the spectra in low frequency range

Dispersive model [3]

Approach: effective lifetime depends on frequency \longrightarrow lifetime distribution

$$\Delta n_1^*(\omega) = \frac{G_1 \tau_0}{1 + (i\omega \tau_0)^{\delta_{disp}}}$$

$$U(\omega) \sim \|\Delta n_1^*(\omega)\|$$

$$\phi(\omega) = -\tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\Im(\Delta n_1^*(\omega))}{\Re(\Delta n_1^*(\omega))} \right)$$

Stieltjes transformation:

$$G(\ln(\tau)) = \frac{1}{2\pi i G_1 \tau_0} \left(\Delta n \left(\frac{e^{-i\pi}}{\tau} \right) - \Delta n \left(\frac{e^{i\pi}}{\tau} \right) \right)$$

\Rightarrow

$$G(\ln(\tau)) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{\sin(\delta_{disp} \pi)}{\cosh \left(\delta_{disp} \ln \left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_0} \right) \right) + \cos(\pi \delta_{disp})}$$

[3] D. W. Davidson, R. H. Cole, J. Chem. Phys 19(12), 1484-1490 (1951)

[4] R. Fuoss, J.G. Kirkwood, J. Am- Chem. Soc. 63(2), 385-394 (1941)

Dispersive model

(i)pm-Si:H/(n)a-Si:H (14 Ωcm)

Dispersive model

(i)pm-Si:H/(n)a-Si:H (14 Ωcm)

shape/wide distribution in low/high
excitation range

Nonlinear approach

linear-to-quadratic recombination regime [5]: **bimolecular model**

solve spherical diffusion equation:
$$\Delta n(r, t) = \frac{G_0 e^{-Lr}}{8\pi Dr} + \frac{G_1 \cos(r \sin(\frac{1}{2}\theta) L \Lambda^{\frac{1}{4}} - \omega t) e^{-L \Lambda^{\frac{1}{4}} \cos(\frac{1}{2}\theta)r}}{8\pi Dr}$$

$$\frac{1}{\tau_{eff}} = \frac{1}{\tau_R} + \frac{1}{\tau_{NR}}$$

$$\Lambda(\omega) := (1 + (\omega\tau_{eff})^2)$$

$$L := \sqrt{D\tau_{eff}}$$

calculate total recombination rate:

$$\theta(\omega) := \arctan(\omega\tau_{eff})$$

$$R(t) = \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{\Delta n(r, t)}{\tau_R} + B \Delta n(r, t)^2 \right) 4\pi r^2 dr$$

$$\longrightarrow S_{IP} = \frac{2}{T} \int_0^T R(t) \cos(\omega t) dt$$

$$S_{OP} = \frac{2}{T} \int_0^T R(t) \sin(\omega t) dt$$

amplitude and phase spectra

Influence of first-overtone (2ω)

$$\Delta n \gg N_A$$

@ 40 Hz:

@ 800 Hz:

Bimolecular model

SiN passivation ($1 \Omega\text{cm}$)

high injection regime: $\Delta n > N_A$

Bimolecular model

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Bimolecular model

SiN passivation (1 Ωcm)

low injection: $\Delta n \ll N_A$

high injection: $\Delta n \gg N_A$

Linear and nonlinear models

SiN passivation ($1 \Omega\text{cm}$)

low injection: $\Delta n \ll N_A$

high injection: $\Delta n \gg N_A$

MPL and measurement of V_{oc}

measurement of V_{oc} by multimeter and MPL

τ_{amp} by MPL

$$V_{oc} \approx \frac{k_B T}{q} \ln \left(\frac{N_A \Delta n + \Delta n^2}{n_0 N_A} \right)$$

$$\Delta n = \Delta p = G \tau_{eff}$$

τ_ϕ by MPL

MPL and measurement of V_{oc}

→ Good agreement between measured V_{oc} and $V_{oc}(\tau_{eff})$ by MPL

Results: Cell

a-Si passivated p-type wafer ($1 \Omega\text{cm}$, $N_A = 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) with TCO

MPL allows measurement on bare wafer and TCO-texture
(via small excitation spot)

Summary

- Modulated photoluminescence promises an efficient method for effective lifetime measurement
- Simple model allows approximation of effective lifetime for low surface recombination and symmetrical samples in low frequency range
- In the case of asymmetrical samples and high surface recombination the exact solution of the diffusion equation leads to a more detailed model
- In case of high excitation (quadratic recombination) modified nonlinear approaches offer a qualitatively better description of spectra
- MPL determined lifetime allows a reliable approximation of V_{oc}
- Advantage of MPL to other lifetime measurements: local investigation of wafers and cells with high doping and backcontacts